

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B091

Date: 21 Apr 2005

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
082021		start posn	0.15 kft	125	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
082112		INU to NAV	0.15 kft	125	
082718		taxy start	0.15 kft	124	
083421		t/o	0.14 kft	211	from cranfield
083555		asp open	2.1 kft	295	
090341	090949	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.26 kft	087	
091045	094133	Run 1	0.36 - 0.29 kft	176	WAS sampling started ~ 20s early
094159	094314	Profile 2	0.29 - -.05 kft	239	
094335	094423	Run 2	-.07 - -.06 kft	239	100 ft
094430	094459	Profile 3.1	-.01 - 0.33 kft	237	
094459	094601	Run 3	0.33 kft		500 ft
094601	094752	Profile 3.2	0.33 - 1.8 kft	268	
094752	094854	Run 4	1.80 kft		2000 ft
094854	095112	Profile 3.3	1.8 - 3.8 kft	269	
095112	095524	Run 5	3.9 - 3.8 kft	270	4000 ft
095525	095741	Profile 3.4	3.8 - 5.8 kft	269	
095741	095842	Run 6	5.9 - 5.8 kft	268	6000 ft
100232	101212	Run 7	2.3 - 2.2 kft	223	
101550	103142	Run 8	2.2 kft	270	
103236	103945	Run 9	3.0 kft	316	
104450	104708	Run 10	1.4 - 1.5 kft	315	
105041	112525	Run 11	0.38 - 0.32 kft	315	
112532	120509	Run 12	0.31 - 0.38 kft	007	
120658	120747	Run 13	-.08 - -.06 kft	339	100 ft
120748	120818	Profile 5.1	-.05 - 0.31 kft	339	
120818	120921	Run 14	0.31 kft	337	500 ft
120921	121049	Profile 5.2	0.41 kft - 1.8 kft	037	
121049	121157	Run 15	1.8 kft	068	2000 ft
121157	121405	Profile 5.3	1.8 kft - 3.8 kft	077	
121405	121506	Run 16	3.8 kft	095	4000 ft
121506	121707	Profile 5.4	3.8 kft - 5.8 kft	095	
121707	121848	Run 17	5.8 kft	094	6000 ft
122003		asp closed	4.7 kft	069	
122904		Land	-.18 kft	121	at Prestwick
123407		Stopped	-.16 kft	030	55'30.46 N, 4'35.95 W
142229		taxy start	-.14 kft	035	
142736		t/o	-.16 kft	301	from Prestwick
142939		asp open	3.1 kft	192	
143327	143623	Run 18	4.6 kft	243	
144139	145920	Run 19	0.37 - 0.35 kft	325	
150041	152259	Run 20	-.01 kft	002	100 ft
152259	150142	Profile 6.1	-.06 kft - 0.28 kft	000	
150142	150223	Run 21	0.28 kft	001	500 ft
150223	150327	Profile 6.2	0.40 kft - 1.8 kft	002	
150327	150508	Run 22	1.8 kft	108	2000 ft
150508	150612	Profile 6.3	1.7 kft - 3.8 kft	153	
150612	150816	Run 23	3.8 kft	097	4000 ft
150816	150947	Profile 6.4	3.7 kft - 5.8 kft	096	
150947	152259	Run 24	5.8 kft	098	6000 ft
152513	152705	Run 25	3.8 - 3.7 kft	101	
153005	154227	Run 26	2.2 kft	094	
154453	161320	Run 27	0.29 kft	094	
161452	161536	Run 28	-.09 - -.08 kft	142	100 ft
161536	161615	Profile 7.1	-.08 - 0.28 kft	141	
161615	161717	Run 29	0.28 kft		500 ft
161717	161853	Profile 7.2	0.31 - 1.8 kft	142	
161853	161955	Run 30	1.8 kft	141	2000 ft
161955	162207	Profile 7.3	1.7 kft - 3.8 kft	142	
162207	16230	Run 31	3.8 kft	139	4000 ft

162309	162528	Profile 7.4	3.7 kft - 5.8 kft	138
162528	162716	Run 32	5.8 - 5.7 kft	142 6000 ft
163223	170235	Run 33	0.29 - 0.32 kft	141
171352		asp closed	6.0 kft	241
173046		Land	0.22 kft	208 at Cranfield
173725		Standstill	0.20 kft	308 52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B091 Track 21-APR-05

TR (Tor)
N 56° 38.5' E 03

Generic Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B091

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date 21-Apr-2005

Outline schedule:

05:30 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:30 – Briefing
08:00 – David Fowler & Alan McDonald collect flight passes
08:30 – Clear aircraft and security check
09:30 – Take off Cranfield
13:30 – Land Prestwick
15:30 – Take off Prestwick
18:30 – Land Cranfield
19:00 – Debrief
19:30 – Power down

Location: Clockwise circumnavigation of England, Wales and Southern Scotland

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols through a round-Britain flight and to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass in E wind direction.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be based on a circumnavigation of England, Wales and Southern Scotland at FL10, hugging the coastline along a pre-defined flight path. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) twice upwind and three times downwind of the source region. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO). These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags. Stop-over at Prestwick airport for refuelling.

Sortie Detail

- a) Take off and climb to FL100 for transit to upwind leg of the operating area.
- b) T+30 descend to FL10 at East point of East Anglia. Start of filter set No 1.
- c) T+60 stop of upwind filter sample; upwind profile (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min^{-1} , level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each), return to FL10 at 2000 ft min^{-1} (approx. 15.5 min profile duration)
- d) T+75.5 start of filter set No 2.
- e) T+85 crossing of Cornwall at 1000ft, terrain following (visibility permitting).
- f) T+105 change to filter set No 3 upon reaching the west coast.
- g) T+135 stop of filter; start of downwind profile No 2 (as before)
- h) T+155 start filter set No 4 at FL10

- i) T+185: end of filter set No 4.
- j) T+185: Downwind profile No 3
- k) T+200.5: start of filter set No 5
- l) T+230: end of filter set No5
- m) T+240 land at Prestwick airport
- n) T+360 T/O at Prestwick airport, return to coast
- o) T+380: start of filter set No 6
- p) T+420: start of filter set No 7
- q) T+450: end filter sampling; Upwind Profile No 4.
- r) T+465.5: start of filter set No 8
- s) T+500: start of filter set No9
- t) T+530: end of filter set No9
- u) T+540: land at Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Foster ?
2. Pilot 2 - Al Roberts ?
3. CCM - Sue Angold
4. CCM2/Cloud Physics – Jamie Trembath
5. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
6. Mission Scientist Training – David Fowler
7. Flight Manager – Alan Wooley
8. Core Chemistry – Ruth Purvis
9. AMS – Jonny Crosier
10. Bag sampling I – Alan McDonald
11. Bag sampling II – Daniela Famulari
12. Filter sampling – Paul James
13. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
14. WAS – Maria Nielsdottir

MAPS:

From 200 - 400m asl Air concentration

CO concentration pattern predicted for 12:00Z based on UK MetOffice UM forecast from Tuesday morning.

Way Points

Cranfield

38
40 52 41N 1 47E
41 51 53N 1 47E
42 51 05N 1 30E
43 50 40N 0 30E
44 50 40N 1 00W
45 50 01N 2 00W
46 50 01N 3 25W
48 50 50N 4 40W
50 51 30N 5 35W
51 52 20N 5 35W
52 53 15N 5 35W
54 53 55N 4 50W

60 54 30N 5 15W
61 55 13N 5 50W

Prestwick

61 55 13N 5 50W
69 56 00N 6 30W
71 56 20N 6 30W
70 56 15N 4 00W
76 56 10N 1 35W
79 55 00N 1 10W
80 54 05N 0 05E
83 53 30N 1 40E
40 52 41N 1 47E

38
Cranfield

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal. Short warm-up time, due to earlier T/O.

In general, the flight followed the pre-defined route and timing. However, flight height and location of the profiles had to be adjusted according to concentration pattern and visibility. After take-off a downward profile was taken at 1000 ft min^{-1} . During this profile the boundary layer height was estimated to be around at about 800 ft and therefore the flight height for the boundary layer flying was adjusted to 500 ft. High concentrations of NO_x , SO_2 , CO and aerosols were observed on the SE corner of the UK and the East part of the Channel. In response the range of the NO_x instrument was increased from 10 ppb to 50 ppb. However, both NO_x and SO_2 topped out in a couple of plumes.

After a profile on the south coast, low clouds prevented the aircraft from returning to 500 ft. And the SW stretch and the crossing of Cornwall were flown at safety altitude of 2500 ft. This is not expected to have compromised the science as this stretch was following the streamlines and presented neither inflow nor outflow for the UK. Northwest of Cornwall flying at 500 ft was resumed. Here outflow plumes were observed in the areas of S Wales, around the Isle of Man and towards the end of flight A, in SW Scotland. A further profile was flown just before the landing cycle in Prestwick started. Here the tephigramme indicated a boundary layer height of about 900 m. Refueling in Prestwick was 15 minutes faster than anticipated. Further polluted outflow airmasses were observed during the first 15 minutes after start out of Prestwick, while amongst the islands, airmasses were clean. Here the route was slightly modified towards the west, to avoid having to rise for the Isle of Islay. A profile was then initiated on the East-bound flight leg, in anticipation of the need to climb for the flight across Scotland, which was initially flown at xxx ft, dropping to xxx ft, halfway across Scotland. NW of Grnagemouth and Edinburgh plumes of large CN concentrations (up to $70,000 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) were observed. On arrival at the East Coast pollutant concentrations initially fell before plumes were observed within an area of stagnant airmasses, possibly influenced by North Sea rigs. Here a further profile was flown, before returning to 500 ft. At moderate wind speeds, concentrations on the southern half of the east coast flight leg became more consistent.

Problems were reported with the filter-pack sampling, due to the loose fit of most of the filter holder disks. It was noted that communication problems arose between the Mission Scientist and the Tedlar bag fillers, who need to be able to talk to each other, either on the training or the isolated channel and therefore cannot hear the MS. It was suggested that during further AMPEP flights, the mission scientist should use the Intercom channel, except when this is set to 'private' during take-off and landing and selected maneuvers. The AMS reported (as yet unspecified) problems during the post-flight calibration at Cranfield.

Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.091A**...

 Date 21-April-05...

Page 1 of 3

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:34		Take-off			hazy, dry cloud top 1500 ft lead, but no cloud above
					Tinian side @ 800 ft
09:03		0950			Profile descent
9:06			P40	here	
9:10:45		Run ①			filter run start
	Run 1 WDS sample				Started somewhat before
9:19		passing		skua line	array
9:20		change of SO ₂ range		from 0-10 to 0-50	
9:41:33		end run 1			
9:41:59		start prof 2			dig down to 50 ft
9:43:					run 2 @ 100 ft
					run 3 @ 500 ft
					Boundary layer height still ~ 800 ft. need to stay above cloud; cloud base < 1000 ft
10:02	Run 6	at 2300 ft			filter start.
10:11					filter sampling interrupted
10:12		end of Run 6			
10:27		cloud tops approaching			flight height of 2.3 kft some OTC plumes
10:32		end of run; climb to 3000 ft			end of run 7
10:45		filter run ③ starts			~ 1000 ft above land
11:18		stop filter run ③			
11:25		start filter run ④			with run 11
11:50		cloud base low, about aircraft height			
12:05		finish run 11 & filter ④			start of profile

CCH

Captain & Co. Chemistry, Flight Manager

C
Left

AL 160

Aircraft Scientist's Log

80

(15th June)

Flight No **B091A**.....

Date **21-Apr-2005**.....

Page **2** of **3**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	Profile	3000	N	5200 4000 ft.	
		00	spikes at	4000!	
	2nd leg of		B091B		
1433 ¹⁰	1436				Booy filming 4300ft Run 14
1441 ³⁰		500			WP 61 - 80 Run 15
					FILTERS BEGAN 1440 approx 15
1452	15	500	N		w/ Ilay 162° 7ms ⁻¹
1458	15	500			Run 15 ends
1500	16	100			R 16 Profile PROFILE 6
1503	17	500			R 17 Profile 2 PROFILE 6
150	17				R 17 ends 1503 PROFILE 6
1504	18	2000'			start 1506 4
1508	18	2000'			STOP 1508.20
1509	18				End of profile 1509 climbing to 6000'
	P6				Profile 1511 6000'
1512					Start of run 6000'
1514				OSAN	Filter run start 1514
1523 ⁰⁰	152 ¹⁹	6000			End of profile 6 - deadstick 4000
1525	16	4000			Start of Run 16
152705	16	4000			End of 16 1527
153005	17	2500			Start of 17 15
15:4235	17	2500			End of run 17

run
Filters (Proc)
3x
chem
CO
BAG-ALL

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.0913...**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **21-04-05**

 Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:44 55	R18	500	E	St Andrews	new low level run No filters
16:13 20	R18	"	S	Newcastle	Stops
16:14 24	R18 PROFIC	100	S	"	Starts
16:16 33	P7	500	S	Teeside	"
16:17 17	P7	500	S		Ends
16:18 23	P7	2000	S		Starts
16:19:41	P7	2000	S		Stops Stops wind 1ms ⁻¹ S
16:22:10	P7	4000	S		Starts wind 0ms ⁻¹ -
16:23:00	P7	4000	S	Guisborough	Stops 4ms wind 283°
16:25:25	R20	6000	S	Robin Hood Bay	Starts
16:27:12	R20	6000	S		End
16:32:24	R22	500	SE	Flamb ^h hd	Starts wind 3ms ⁻¹ 135°
16:42:45	R22	500	SE	Spurn hd	4ms ⁻¹ 103°
16:47	R22	500	SE	E S on sea	5ms ⁻¹ 123°
16:52:42	R22	500	SE	E Skerries	turning to avoid sea bunk
16:56:20	R22	500	S	"	5ms ⁻¹ 114° 2.8ppb NO ₂ , 0.5ppb
17:02	R22	500	S	Emmer	Run 22 stops
					Climbing to 6000 ft
17:06	—				Some samples at 6000 ft
17:09	—	6000	W	Wormer	End of Run
					Returning to Cranfield

 LAST BATCH
 AFTER SON

Tanase - cloud physics (CCME)
Sue - CCM1

Flight No: B091

Date: 21 April 2005

Tedlar bag operator(s): D. Famulari, A. McDonald // bags

GMT

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
05-515	9:55:55	9:12	52.4	1.7 E	Maybe 08-515 1st profile
05-224	9:10:48	9:11:08	52.3	1.7	500ft
05-525	9:12:15	9:12:45	52.2	1.7	Flow rate reduced
05-537	9:13:15	9:13:44	52.2	1.7	
05-228	9:14:17	9:14:47	52.1	1.7	
05-227	9:15:15	9:15:45	52.0	1.7	
05-221	9:16:20	9:16:50	52.0	1.7	
05-223	9:17:20	9:17:50	51.9	1.7	
05-522	9:18:25	9:18:55	51.9	1.7	
05-230	9:19:20	9:19:50	51.8	1.7	Passing ferry.
05-225	9:20:20	9:20:50	51.7	1.7	
05-226	9:21:20	9:21:50	51.7	1.7	
05-544	9:22:20	9:22:50	51.6	1.7	
05-524	9:23:20	9:23:50	51.6	1.6	
05-523	9:24:20	9:24:50	51.5	1.6	
05-229	9:25:20	9:25:44	51.5	1.6	
05-548	9:26:20	9:26:50	51.4	1.6	
05-549	9:27:25	9:27:55	51.4	1.6	
05-539	9:28:20	9:28:50	51.3	1.5	
05-547	9:29:20	9:29:50	51.2	1.5	
05-545	9:30:20	9:30:50	51.2	1.5	
05-550	9:31:20	9:31:50	51.1	1.5	
05-530	9:32:20	9:32:50	51.1	1.5	
05-521	9:33:20	9:33:50	51.0	1.4	
05-324	9:34:20	9:34:50	51.0	1.4	
05-325	9:35:20	9:35:50	51.0	1.3	
05-214	9:36:20	9:36:50	50.9	1.1	
05-209	9:37:20	9:37:50	50.9	1.1	
05-322	9:38:20	9:38:20	50.8	1.0	
05-323	9:39:20	9:39:50	50.8	0.9	
05-208	9:40:25	9:40:55	50.8	0.8	
05-540	9:42:45	9:43:15	50.7	0.7	New profile No2
05-530	9:43:31	9:44:01	50.7	0.6	
05-321	9:45:00	9:45:30	50.7	0.5	
05-529	9:47:55	9:48:25	50.6	0.2	2000 ft?
05-529	9:51:15	9:51:45	50.6	0.0E	4000ft
05-546	9:52:20	9:52:50	50.6	0.2W	4000ft
05-527	9:53:45	9:54:15	50.6	0.3W	4000ft
05-543	9:57:45	9:58:15	50.6	0.7	6000ft

Flight No: BB91-A

Date: 21 APRIL 2005

Tedlar bag operator(s): D. FAMULARI, A. McDONALD

GMT

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
05-533	10:15:55	10:16:25	49.9	2.0W	
05-326	10:16:55	10:17:25	49.9	2.1	Inc Samp freq to 15 sec?
05-526	10:17:55	10:18:25	49.9	2.3	2000ft - can't drop low eno.
05-338	10:19:40	10:20:10	50.0	2.4	
05-327	10:21:00	10:21:30	49.9	2.5	
05-328	10:22:00	10:22:30	50.0	2.7	
05-212	10:23:00	10:23:30	50.0	2.8	
05-213	10:24:00	10:24:30	50.0 49.9	2.9	
05-236	10:25:00	10:25:30	50.0	2.9	
05-329	10:26:00	10:26:30	50.0	3.0	
05-339	10:27:00	10:27:30	49.9	3.1	
05-267	10:28:00	10:28:30	50.0	3.2	
05-265	10:29:05	10:29:35	50.0	3.3	
05-264	10:30:00	10:30:30	50.0	3.4	
05-215	10:31:00	10:31:30	50.0	3.5	
05-340	10:32:40	10:33:10	50.1	3.6	End 2000ft
05-233	10:33:40	10:34:10	50.2	3.7	3000ft
05-235	10:34:40	10:35:10	50.2	3.7	(Over low all)
05-234	10:35:40	10:36:10	50.2	3.8	
05-216	10:36:40	10:37:10	50.3	3.9	
05-217	10:37:40	10:38:10	50.3	3.9	
05-263	10:38:40	10:39:10	50.4	4.0	
05-262	10:39:40	10:40:10	50.4	4.1	
05-261	10:44:55	10:45:25	50.7	4.4	Dep to 1000ft.
05-270	10:45:55	10:46:25	50.7	4.5	
05-269	10:46:55	10:47:25	50.7	4.6	
05-266	10:51:00	10:51:15	50.9	4.8	15 sec Down to 500ft
05-268	10:51:30	10:51:45	50.9	4.9	
05-330	10:52:10	52:30			
05-218	10:52:30	53:30	51.0	4.9	
05-220	10:53:30	53:50	51.0	5	
05-211					
05-219	10:54:40	55:00	51.1	5.1	
05-237	10:55:50	56:10	51.2	5.1	
05-238	? 30	50			
05-240	10:57:40	57:00	51.2	5.2	
05-347	58:00	54:20			
05-239	59:50	50:10	51.3	5.4	
05-312	11:01:10	11:01:30	51.4	5.5	

05-266 →

3

Flight No: 8091-A

Date: 2/4/05

Tedlar bag operator(s): FAMULARI / McDONALD

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
05-311	11:01:50	11:02:10	51.4	5.5	
05-313	11:02:30	11:02:50	51.5	5.5	
05-314	11:03:00	11:03:20	51.5	5.5	
05-316	11:03:30	11:07:50	51.6	5.5	
05-315	11:04:10	11:04:30			
05-536	11:04:50	11:05:10	51.6	5.5	
05-542	11:05:30	11:05:50	51.7	5.5	
05-534	11:06:10	11:06:30	"	"	
05-535	11:06:41	11:07:01	"	"	
05-272	11:07:20	11:07:40	51.8	5.5	
05-273	11:08:00	11:08:20	51.8	5.5	
05-271	11:08:30	11:08:50	"	"	
05-328	11:09:00	11:09:20	51.9	5.5	
05-348	11:09:35	11:09:55	"	"	
05-516	11:10:10	11:10:30	"	"	
05-517	11:10:45	11:10:05	52.0	5.5	
05-541	40	00	"	"	
532	20	40			
531	50	10			
206	11:13:20	11:13:40	52.1	5.5	
232	11:14:00	11:14:20			
231	11:15:20	15:40	52.2	5.5	
331	15:50	16:10			
210	11:16:20	16:40	52.3	5.5	
204	11:16:50	17:10			
205	11:17:20	17:40			
207	11:18:00	11:18:20	52.4	5.4	
203	11:18:30	11:18:50			
202	11:19:00	11:19:20	52.4	5.5	
201	11:19:30	11:19:50			
332	20:00	20:20	52.5	5.5	
486	20:30	20:50			
485	21:00	21:20	52.5	5.4	
484	11:21:30	11:21:50			
483	22:00	22:20	52.6	5.4	
482	11:22:30	11:22:50			
481	23:00	23:20	52.7	5.4	
490	11:23:30	23:50			
489	24:00	24:20	52.7	5.4	

④

Flight No: B091-A

Date: 21/4/05

Tedlar bag operator(s): MCDONALD / FAMULARI

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
488	11:24:30	11:24:50	52.7	5.4	
487	11:25:00	25:20			
333	11:25:40	26:00			
334	11:26:10	26:30	52.8	5.4	
336	11:26:40	11:27:00			
335	11:27:20	27:40	52.9	5.4	
337	11:27:50	28:10			
222	28:20	28:40	53.0	5.4	
291	11:28:50	11:29:10			
317	4 29:20	11:29:40			
298	11:29:50	11:30:10	53.0	5.4	
299	11:30:20	11:30:40			
300	11:30:50	11:31:10	53.1	5.4	
297	11:31:20	11:31:40			
349	11:31:50	11:32:10	53.2	5.4	
296	11:32:20	11:32:40			
314	33:00 11:33:00	11:33:20	53.2	5.4	
274	11:33:30	11:33:50			
278	11:34:00	11:34:20	53.3	5.3	
276	11:34:30	11:34:50			
277	11:35:00	11:35:20	53.4	5.3	
278	11:35:30	35:50			
279	11:36:00	11:36:20	53.4	5.3	
280	36:30	11:36:50			
346	37:00	11:37:20	53.5	5.2	
345	37:30	11:37:50			
344	11:38:00	11:38:20	53.5	5.2	
342	11 38:30	11 38:50			
343	11:39:00	39:20	53.6	5.1	
341	39:30	39:50			
375	40:05	40:25	"	"	
374	11:40:40	11:41:00			
301	11:41:10	41:30	53.6	5.0	
028	11:41:40	42:00			
295	11:42:10	42:30	53.7	5.0	
05-294	11:42:40	11:43:00			
292	43:00	43:20	53.8	4.9	
293	11:43:50	44:10			
320	44:30	44:50	"	"	

11:44:35 44:55

5

Flight No: B091-A

Date: 2/4/05

Tedlar bag operator(s): FAMULARI | McDONALD

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
290	11:45:05	45:25	53.8	4.8	
289	45:35	11:45:55			
281	46:05	46:25	53.9	4.8	
304	46:35	11:46:55			
305	11:47:10	11:47:30	53.9	4.9	
288	11:47:40	48:00			
287	11:48:20	48:40	54.0	4.9	
307	48:50	11:49:10			
286	11:49:30	11:49:50	54.1	5.0	
292	50:00	50:20			
372	11:50:40	11:51:00	54.1	5.0	372
373	11:51:10	11:51:30			
285	51:40	52:00	54.2	5.0	
371	52:10	52:30			
303	52:40	53:00	54.2	5.1	
302	53:10	53:30			
358	53:40	54:00			
360	54:10	54:30	54.3	5.1	
361	54:40	55:00			
357	55:12	55:32	54.4	5.2	
359	55:40	56:00			
283	11:56:10	11:56:30	54.4	5.2	
284	11:56:40	11:57:00			
356	57:10	57:30			
355	57:40	58:00	54.5	5.3	
362	58:14	58:34			
363	58:40	59:00	54.6	5.3	
364	59:10	11:59:30			
366	11:59:40	12:00:00			
365	12:00:10	00:30	54.7	5.4	
251	12:00:40	12:01:00			
306	12:01:10	01:30	54.7	5.4	
308	01:40	02:00			
173	12:02:10	02:30	54.8	5.?	
351	02:40	03:00			
258	12:03:10	12:03:30	54.8	5.5	
259	12:03:40	04:00			
172	12:04:10	04:30	54.9	5.6	
171	12:04:40	12:05:00			

Second part of the flight Flight No: B091-B

Date: 2/1/04/2005

Tedlar bag operator(s): Daniela Famulani, Alan McDonald

white bag container

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
480	14:34:10	14:34:20			
474	14:34:40	14:35:10			
447	14:35:10	14:36:00			
448	14:36:35	14:36:55			
420	14:37:20	14:37:45	55.2	5.5	905 mb
431	14:38:00	14:38:20			
440	14:38:40	14:39:00			
446	14:39:20	14:39:40	55.2	5.6	
556	40:10	40:40			
	41:10	41:40			bag that went without writing, imadite
462	42:10	42:40			
467	43:10	43:40			
494	44:10	44:40			
419	45:10	45:40	55.4	6.1	Islay haar, 6mm
497	46:10	46:40			
496	47:10	47:40			
466	48:10	48:40	55.5	6.3	
418	49:10	49:40			
463	50:10	50:40			
491	51:10	51:40	55.6	6.5	8 m/s 155° 1000 mb
504	52:10	52:40			
554	53:10	53:40	55.8	6.5	7 m/s 172°
417	54:10	54:40			
465	55:10	55:40	55.9	6.5	
499	56:10	56:40			
513	57:10	57:40			
512	58:10	58:40	56.1	6.5	
511	59:10	59:40			
464	15:00:45	15:01:15			
520	15:02:25	02:55	56.3	6.5	0.3 kft
498	15:05:40	05:00			2000 ft mm
519	15:08:30	08:00			
518	15:12:00	12:30	56.2	5.7	6000 ft (5000) 10 m/s 148°
500	13:10	13:40	56.2	5.6	
461	16:00	16:30	56.2	5.3	
493	17:00	17:30	56.2	5.2	
492	18:00	18:30	56.2	5.1	
551	19:00	19:30			
555	20:00	20:30	56.2	4.8	

Flight No: B091 - B

Date: 2/04/05

Tedlar bag operator(s): Daniela Fannucini Alan McDonald

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
490	21:10	21:40	56.2	4.8	5.6
553	22:00	22:30	56.2	4.7	
552	24:00	24:30			4.4 kf
469	25:00	25:30	56.2	4.4	3.6 kf (end of 4000ft)
468	26:00	26:30	56.2	4.3	
432	28:00	28:30		4	
416	29:00	29:30			
433	30:00	30:30	56.2	3.9	2.2 kf
434	31:15	31:45			
435	32:00	32:30			
410	33:00	33:30	56.2	3.6	2.2
445	34:00	34:30			
444	35:00	35:30	56.2	3.3	2.2 4 ms, 185°
436	36:00	36:30			
437	37:00	37:30	56.2	3.2	
438	38:00	38:30			4 M/s 171°
439	39:00	39:30	56.2	3.0	
423	40:00	40:30	"	2.9	pure Fife air
424	41:00	41:30	"		
558	42:10	42:40	"	2.6	end of run & descent to 500 ft
441	43:00	43:30			1000 ft (down to
425	44:00	44:30			1000
560	45:00	45:30			
559	46:00	46:30			100
418	47:00	47:30	56.1	2.1	5 m/s, 122°
442	48:00	48:30			
414	49:00	49:30			4 ms 122° 0.2 kft
481	50:00	50:30			
428	51:00	51:30			
428	52:00	52:30	56.1	1.7	
413	53:00	53:30			
7482 452	54:00	54:30	56.0	1.6	0.2 kft
454	55:00	55:30			
412	56:00	56:30	55.9	1.6	1 ms 103°
453	57:00	57:30	55.8	1.5	
411	58:00	58:30			
422	59:00	59:30			
485 455	16:00:00	00:30	55.7	1.4	1 m/s 106°
427	16:01:00	01:30	55.7	1.4	

Flight No: B091 - B

Date: 21/04/2005

Tedlar bag operator(s): Daniela Fanculani, Alan McDonald

Bag No	Time on	Time off	East/Lat	North/Long	Comments
OS -430	16:02:00	02:30	55.6	1.4	0.2 kft
456	03:00	03:30	55.5	1.4	0.3 kft
445	04:00	04:30			
421	05:00	05:30	55.4	1.3	0.2
426	06:00	06:30	55.4	1.3	0.3
457	07:00	07:30	55.3	1.3	
458	08:00	08:30			
400	09:00	09:30	55.2	1.2	
459	10:00	10:30			
399	11:00	11:30	55	1.2	
460	12:00	12:30			
398	13:00	13:30			end of run to soft
397	14:20	14:55			
396	15:07	15:37			100 ft
395	16:20	16:50			500 ft
394	19:00	19:30			climb to 2000 ft
393	20:10	20:40			climb to 4000 ft
391	21:30	22:00			
392	22:15	22:45			run
510	23:20	23:50	54.5	0.5	prof. to 6000
509	25:00	25:30			at 6000 ft
508	25:50	26:20			at 6000 ft
507	27:00	27:30			at 6000 ft then descend
506	16:32:30	32:00	54.0	0.10	back at 500 ft (adding 0.2 kft)
505	16:33:30	34:00	54.0	0.1E	
504	34:20	35:00			wind 104° / 3 m/s
503	35:30	36:00	53.9	0.2E	
502	36:30	37:00			
501	37:30	38:00			
390	38:31	39:01			102° / 3 m/s
381	39:30	40:00	53.9	0.5E	
382	40:30	41:00			
383	41:30	42:00			
384	42:30	43:00			106° / 4 m/s
385	43:30	44:00	53.7	0.8E	
386	44:30	45:00			
387	45:40	46:10			
388	46:30	47:00			
389	47:30	48:00			

FLIGHT B091

DATE 21/5/04

PAGE 1

	Sample ID	Start time (UTC)	Stop time (UTC)	Comulative volume (m3)	Comments
T	¹⁴¹ 1130/93	08:43	8:56		Back ground
B	115/98/16	08:45	8:56		Back ground
T	83 133/141	9:10:45	9 41 33	Blot 1382	Run 1 filter paper not seated properly
B	97/86/135	9:10:45	9 41 33	1279 570	Run 1
T	84/136/141	10 03:00	10 31	244 ²⁴⁴ 1087	Run 2 Interrest run, continue 1024
B	52/160/18	10:03:00	10 31	244 520	Run 2.
T	157/88/141	10:04: ⁴⁵ 50	11 18	1277	Run 3
B	51/126/87	10:04: ⁴⁵ 50	11 18	608.	Run 3
T	90/155	11 25 32	12 05	1639	Run 4
B	120/149/142	11 25 32	12 05	725	Run 4
T	134/113/141	14 43	16 03	806	Filter set 5.
B	140/151/10	14 43	16 03	383	filter set 6
T	85/132/141	15 12	15 45	1047	filter set 7
B	129/123/18	15 45 15 12	15 45	546	filter set 7 filter paper advice

FLIGHT NUMBER B091AB	DATE: 21/4/04	OPERATOR: RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP		

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	81	143	134
POST FLIGHT			

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.4	0.45	1.121	0.068	0.480
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
OK	34.17	1.30	7.17	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	0	0	0	1	-1	0	
NO (ppbV)	0.015	0.07	-0.04	-0.02	0.02	0.06	
NO ₂ (ppbV)	-0.13	-0.15	-0.18	-0.15	-0.15	-0.14	
NO _x (ppbV)	-0.08	-0.08	-0.22	-0.17	-0.13	-0.08	
SO ₂ (ppbV)	-1.03	-1.25	-0.51	-0.77	-0.34	-1.06	

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
NO _x taking a long time to zero – tubing on trap dirty

FLIGHT NUMBER B091AB	DATE: 21/4/04	OPERATOR: RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP		

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)		Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	
08:58:43	5000	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		86.54	82.95	7177.92			
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
9:15:39	500ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		84.65	84.84	7181.89	49.29	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.96	0.4	0.45	1.119	0.066	0.482		
10:19:41	2000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		84.76	84.49	7160.72	49.90	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.90	0.4	0.45	1.12	0.067	0.456		
11:16:38	500 ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		85.07	83.92	7138.85	49.90	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
34.26	0.4	0.45	0.066	1.123	0.480		
14:44:35	500 ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		81.77	85.38	6981.10	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.95	0.4	0.45	1.109	0.066	0.481		

FLIGHT NUMBER B091AB	DATE: 21/4/04	OPERATOR: RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP		

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
15:40:39	2400ft	84.52	82.73	6992.58	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.5	0.45	1.112	0.069	0.457
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
16:41:02	500 ft	85.53	81.31	6954.43	50	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.91	0.4	0.45	1.115	0.069	0.481
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER	B091AB	DATE:	21/4/04	OPERATOR:	RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP					

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

10:21 SO2 range changes from 10 ppbV to 50 ppbV

Nox chamber alarm keeps coming on for a few seconds but only 0.1 degree too high!

Taken a long time for the Co lamp to warm up to 50 degrees – may need to investigate, although the pumps were not on for warm up so aircraft was a lot cooler

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B091

Date: 21/04/05

Operator: JT

Page 1 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
											N.B. FFSSP heater still Non Op
09:03:41	Non-Op		0	Not asked for	Not asked for			Not asked for			Profile 1 decent FL50
09:04:38			0								FL40
09:05:45			0								FL30
09:07:03			0								FL20
09:08:09			0								FL10
09:09:01			0								500ft
09:10:45			0								Run 1 500ft
09:41:33			0								End of run 1
09:42:00			0								Start Profile 2 decent 500ft to 50ft
09:43:25			0								Profile 3 ascent 50ft to 100ft end
09:43:25			0								Run (1) 100ft start
09:44:23			0								Profile 3 100ft to 500ft end
09:45:00			0								Run (2) 500ft end
09:46:00			0								Profile 3 500ft to 1000ft end
09:47:00			0								Run (3) 1000ft end
09:47:52			0								Profile 3 1000ft to 2000ft end
09:48:53			0								Run (4) 2000ft end
09:51:10			0								Profile 3 2000ft to 4000ft end
09:55:24			0								Run (5) 4000ft end
09:57:40			0								Profile 3 4000ft to 6000ft end
09:58:43			0								Run (6) 6000ft end
10:02:32			0								Run 6 2200ft start
10:12:12			0								Run 6 2200ft end
10:12:23			0								Start profile 4 descent 2200ft to
10:13:25			18								1200 ft
10:13:58			22								End P4 Climb back to 2200ft from
10:15:30			27								800ft
10:15:52			27								2200ft
10:31:43			27								2200ft run 7 start (actual 2400ft)
10:32:35			27								Run 7 end climb to FL30
											Run 8 FL30

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B091a

Date: 21/04/05

Operator: JT

Page 3 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:33:27			0	Prob checking	Ffssp wind	Blew all	H20	Away no	signal		Run 14 4500ft start
14:36:23			0								End of run
14:41:39			0								Run 15 start 500ft
14:59:20			0								End of run 15
											Profile 50 to 100ft
15:00:45			0								Run at 100ft start
15:01:43			0								Profile 100 to 500ft start
15:02:22			0								Run 500ft start
15:03:28			0								Profile 500 to 2000ft start
15:05:07			0								Run 2000ft start
15:06:10			0								Profile 2000ft to 4000ft start
15:08:14			0								Run 4000ft start
15:09:46			0								Profile 4000ft to 6000ft start
15:11:50			0			Restartd	ffssp	No data in	Cloud		Run 6000ft start
15:15:00			1								
15:17:00			5								
15:19:00			8								
15:21:00			8								
15:22:59			8								End of profile / runs
15:25:13			8								Start run 16 4000ft
15:27:05			8								Stop run
15:30:15			8								Start run 17 2400ft
15:42:28			8								End of run 17
15:44:53			8								Start run 18 500ft
16:13:20			8								End of run 18
16:14:26			8								Start of profile 50 to 100ft
16:14:45			8								Run 100 ft start
16:15:34			8								Profile 100 to 500ft start
16:16:14			8								Run 500ft start
16:17:17			8								Profile 500ft to 2000ft start
16:18:53			8								Run 2000ft start
16:19:54			8								Profile 2000ft to 4000ft start

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B091**

Date: 21/04/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	N
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	N
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	N
Heimann		Y	SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	N	
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	Racks:		
Nevzorov		Y	INC	N	
TWC		Y	CCN / CNC		Y
FWVS		N	CVI	Y	N
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	N	
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
Lower Clear	Y	Y			
“ Red	Y	Y			
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N				
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			<u>Others:</u>		
TAFTS		N	NIR TDLAS	Y	N
MARSS		N	2BT O3	Y	N
DEIMOS		N	VACC	Y	N
ARIES		N	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SWS		N	Formaldehyde	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			ADA	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ECGC	N		NOxy	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	PTRMS		Y
CO	Y	Y	Bag Sampling		Y
ORAC	Y	N			
PAN	Y	N			
PERCA	Y	N			
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B091

Date: 21/04/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off (mysteriously fixed self in flight...!).
2. Radalt – reading zero feet on ascent after take off. Fixed by breaking and making pfw dlu c/b.
3. Preset derived data plots missing from both FM and Core Chem pcs
4. Core 2 and Core 3 computers not seen on Network Neighbourhood. Fixed by copying vserver.vxd file from core1 c:\windows\system to core 2 and 3 machines (pre-flight)
5. Filters flow drs bits always at max DRS value, even when flow off.

Aircraft

Satcom-H calls made by FM: 1

Filters radio box faulty on transmit. Ok to receive